

Kinetics of Oxidation of Isopropyl Alcohol by Cerium (IV)

D. L. Mathur and G. V. Bakore

The kinetics of the oxidation of isopropyl alcohol by cerium (IV) in dilute nitric acid medium have been studied. The reaction goes through a radical process as suggested by Ardon. The thermodynamic parameters of cerium (IV)—isopropyl alcohol have been evaluated. The effect of hydrogen and nitrate ion concentrations on the rate has been studied and results explained on the basis of $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}$ as the reactive species.

Sethuram and Muhammad¹ have recently studied the oxidation of isopropyl alcohol by cerium (IV) in nitric acid. The work of said authors suggest that the reaction goes through a radical process as suggested by Ardon². An increase in hydrogen ion concentration at constant ionic strength accelerated the rate of oxidation while nitrate ions were found to retard the rate of oxidation. The rate was found to be inversely proportional to the square of the nitrate ion concentrations. The authors¹ have assumed $[\text{Ce}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$ as the reactive species of cerium (IV). The present paper reports some additional data on the oxidation of isopropyl alcohol by cerium (IV) in nitric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

B.D.H. "AnalaR" isopropyl alcohol (purified by fractionation), Ceric ammonium nitrate (A.E.C., India) and nitric acid (A.R., Oster, India) were used. Ionic strength was maintained by potassium nitrate. The reaction was followed by usual titrimetric methods³ under pseudo first order conditions with the alcohol in large excess. The observed rate constant k_1 was calculated from graphs. The results obtained on varying the alcohol concentration are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Variation of Rate with Concentration of Alcohol
 $[\text{Ce}(\text{IV})] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Temperature = 25°
 $[\text{HNO}_3] = 1.08 M$

[Alcohol] $\times 10^2$ moles litre ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹
5.0	1.46
10.0	2.66
15.0	3.81
20.0	4.83
25.0	5.72

1. B. Sethuram and S. S. Muhammad, *Acta. Chim. Hung.*, 1965, **46**, 115, 125.
2. M. Ardon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1811.
3. J. Shorter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1868.

The plot of $1/k_1$ Vs. $1/[\text{ROH}]$ gave a straight line which did not pass through the origin. This suggests an intermediate cerium (IV)—alcohol complex. The results fit in a equation :

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{k[\text{Ce(IV)}][\text{Alcohol}]}{1/K + [\text{Alcohol}]} = k_1[\text{Ce(IV)}]$$

which gives the value of formation constant K for the complex as 1.62 litre mole⁻¹ and a decomposition rate constant $k = 1.94 \times 10^{-3}$ min⁻¹ at 25°. By repeating the procedure at different temperatures, the formation constants of the complex have been evaluated as 1.26 and 0.97 litre mole⁻¹ at 30° and 35° respectively. From the plot of $\log K$ Vs. $1/T$, the values of ΔH , ΔF and ΔS for the complex formation process have been determined as -8.18 k.cal. mole⁻¹, -284.0 cal.mole⁻¹ and -26.51 e.u. respectively at 25° and 1.08 M nitric acid.

At constant ionic strength $\mu = 1.85M$, the rate of oxidation decreases with increase in hydrogen ion concentration and a plot of $1/k_1$ Vs. $[\text{H}^+]$ gave a straight line (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Variation of Rate with Concentration of Hydrogen ions
 $[\text{Ce(IV)}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ Temperature = 25°
 $[\text{Alcohol}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}M$

$[\text{H}^+]$ moles litre ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹
0.45	1.67
0.85	1.52
1.05	1.45
1.45	1.35
1.65	1.25
1.85	1.20

The addition of nitrate ions was found to inhibit oxidation to a small but distinct extent and not so strong as suggested¹. With an addition of potassium nitrate from 0.0 M to 1.0 M the value of k_1 changed from 5.31 to 4.90×10^{-3} min⁻¹ at 35° and 0.50 M nitric acid.

The variation of rate constants with temperature are given in Table 3. The apparent heat of activation obtained by a plot of $\log k_1$, Vs. $1/T$ was 22.5 k.cal.

TABLE 3

Effect of Temperature on the Rate
 $[\text{Ce(IV)}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ $[\text{HNO}_3] = 1.08 M$
 $[\text{Alcohol}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}M$

Temperature °K	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹
298	1.45
303	2.65
308	4.62
313	8.94

DISCUSSIONS

The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the rate finds an explanation on the basis of the following equilibrium :

assuming $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}$ as the reactive species of cerium (IV). At the total concentration of cerium (IV) used, concentration of dimer being negligibly small and cerium (IV) existing mostly as $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}$ and Ce^{4+} . The small effect of the concentration of hydrogen ions on the rate of oxidation suggests that the value of the equilibrium constant K_h for the reaction (1) is small. If the reaction (1) is valid and $[\text{Ce}(\text{IV})]$ represents the total concentration of cerium (IV), we have :

$$[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}] + [\text{Ce}^{4+}] = [\text{Ce}(\text{IV})]$$

and

$$1/k_1 = [\text{H}^+]/K' \cdot K_h + 1/K' \quad \dots (2)$$

where K' is a constant which includes the concentration of alcohol which is kept constant. From the slope-intercept of the straight line obtained between $1/k_1$ and $[\text{H}^+]$, the value of K_h was calculated as 3.58 at 25°.

The inhibitory influence of nitrate ions may be explained on the basis of conversion of more reactive species $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}$ into less reactive species $[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})\text{NO}_3]^{2+}$ which also supports the observations of Shorter³.

Isopropyl alcohol on oxidation by cerium (IV) gives acetone which was identified and estimated colorimetrically by the method described by Mino, Kaizerman and Rasmussen⁴. The oxidation proceeds through a radical process as suggested by Ardon².

Department of Chemistry,
University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur.

Received August 25, 1970

4. G. Mino, S. Kaizerman and E. Rasmussen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 1494.